

Table 2. Evolution of CO₂ in BGA and azolla nurseries at TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India, Jun-Sep 1992.

Source	CO ₂ evolved (mg/m ²)	
	12 h ^a	24 h
Control	120 (10) ^b	240 (10)
BGA nursery	550 (46)	1100 (46)
Azolla nursery	480 (40)	1460 (61)

^a0600-1800. ^bFigures in parentheses denote CO₂ evolved (mg/h per m²).

Biomass and N content of *Sesbania rostrata* mutant with long vegetative phase

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TSR-1 (Trombay *S. rostrata*-1), the late-flowering mutant of *S. rostrata*, remains insensitive to critical inductive photoperiod up to 60 d after planting (DAP). It has the potential to produce sufficient biomass regardless of time of sowing.

We evaluated the performance of TSR-1, the parent cultivar, and local

to atmospheric pollution, increased DOC in water associated with biofertilizers might alleviate problems related to stagnant water. Augmenting DOC in continuously submerged fields where BGA and azolla are grown might also eliminate accumulated reduced iron and sulfides, which are toxic to rice. ■

S. aculeata variety during short-day months of Jan and Feb and long-day months of Jun and Jul. *S. sesban* was included in the Jun-Jul study. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Net plot size was 2.3 m². Plant height, fresh weight, percent N, and N/plant were determined at 50 DAP.

TSR-1 was significantly superior to its parent and *S. aculeata* for biomass and N/plant during Jan-Feb (Table 1). During Jun-Jul, TSR-1 performed as well as its parent and the other species for all parameters; it had marginal superiority for N/plant (Table 2). TSR-1 can be grown for biomass production during months of long or short photoperiods. ■

Table 1. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jan-Feb, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N (whole plant)	N/plant (g)
<i>S. rostrata</i>	90.0	2.5	3.7	6.12
TSR-1	126.5	4.1	3.6	9.33
<i>S. aculeata</i>	93.5	1.6	3.6	4.19
LSD (0.05)	18.8	0.5	0.7	2.99

Table 2. Data from yield trial of TSR-1, Jun-Jul, Bombay, India.

Variety/species	Plant height (cm)	Fresh weight (kg/plot)	% N		N/plant (g)
			Leaf	Stem	
<i>S. rostrata</i>	187.5	6.1	5.6	1.7	0.92
TSR-1	186.5	6.0	5.4	1.8	1.22
<i>S. sesban</i>	132.3	6.0	5.4	1.4	0.87
<i>S. aculeata</i>	165.3	5.9	5.2	1.9	1.12
LSD (0.01)	33.8	1.6	0.4	0.6	0.38

Integrated pest management—diseases

Analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of bacterial blight (BB) pathogen in West Java, Indonesia

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo), is the most important disease of lowland rice in Indonesia in the wet season. To develop high-yielding varieties with durable resistance to BB, it is necessary to understand the pathogen population structure. We conducted an initial analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of Xoo in West Java using molecular marker techniques.

1. TNX1 haplotypes defined from the Indonesian Xoo isolates (A-D) and the predominant haplotype (III-B) observed for race 3 in Central Luzon, Philippines. M = DNA molecular weight markers.